

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D1.4 Intermediary Report on Data Management Plan

Call and Topic: HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02

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- EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is an intermediate report on the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the INTEGER project. Its objective is to describe how data is handled during the INTEGER project and along the required 5 years period, after the project ends.

The DMP is guided by different factors:

- i) Legal framework,
- ii) Open data policy (FAIR approach),
- iii) Project needs (what kind of data is needed and used during the project).

Based on these three aspects, a strategy and procedures for handling data in the project have been defined, specially taking into account the GDPR and national laws of each partner that must be known and correctly applied.

This document consists of four main parts.

- 1) Sections 1 and 2 introduce what data management, open access and the FAIR concept are. These are the standards and the approach adopted by the project as part of a Horizon Europe CSA¹.
- 2) Section 3 presents what data is used, its purpose and how it is identified. This includes the metadata, which are the files describing the dataset that is used.
- 3) The third part, Section 4, presents the procedures that are followed to manage data. This section describes the overall structure and the defined procedures for data management.
- 4) Finally, Section 5 gives an overview (short description) of the datasets that are planned to be used in INTEGER.

The document is complemented by conclusions and annexes, where an example of the informed consent and datasets can be found.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

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– SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DPC	Data Protection Coordinator
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	FAIR principle for open data: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1 Data Management Framework

1.1 Introduction

The INTEGER DMP describes in detail what data the project collects/generates and is collected/generated, what data is shared or made open and how the data is described. It also identifies the data protection laws and regulations at national² and EU and national³ level that must be followed and the methodologies for protecting the data. As a European project, INTEGER defines the recommendations to be followed to make research data compliant with the FAIR approach. Finally, the DMP also proposes a management structure, procedures, and what tools and resources can be used to maintain and preserve the data during and after the project lifetime.

1.2 General overview

The three points to consider when dealing with data in INTEGER are: The Open Access of publications, Open Data, and the IPR restrictions included in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. As a general rule, partners must take into account that unless it goes against the legitimate interest of the beneficiaries, the results must be open and disseminated to the society and scientific community. This means that the beneficiaries have the right to protect the results in case the institution plans to protect or exploit the results. In the following subsections, it is provided in more detail on how it is recommended (by the European Commission) to open access and data within a Horizon Europe project.

1.2.1 Open Access in Horizon Europe

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing, free of charge to any user, online access to all peer-reviewed scientific information and all research data. Accordingly, as stated in Article 17 of the Grant Agreement (GA), consortium members must:

- *no later than the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a reliable repository of scientific publications,*
- *immediate open access to the deposited publication is provided through the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and,*
- *through the repository, information about any research results is given, , or any other tool and instrument needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.*

²https://commission.europa.eu/aid-development-cooperation-fundamental-rights/your-rights-eu/know-your-rights/freedoms/protection-personal-data_en

³ https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb/members_en

To ensure open access, it has been agreed to use OpenAIRE⁴ to link different Zenodo⁵ repositories. OpenAIRE and Zenodo are both free resources developed with the objective of helping the EU scientific and research community to comply with regulations, offer secure datasets and publication exchange services, gain visibility and facilitate reporting with EC's public grants programs (i.e Horizon Europe).

1.2.2 Open Data in Horizon Europe

Also as stated in the GA (Article 17) each beneficiary must ensure open access⁶ to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- *As soon as possible and within the deadlines, set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated and compliant with the European Open Science Cloud⁷ (EOSC),*
- *As soon as possible and within the deadlines, set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a license with equivalent rights, following the principle ‘as open as possible as closed as necessary’, unless providing open access would in particular: be against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests, or the beneficiary’s obligations under the Grant and Consortium Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified and registered in the Datasets spreadsheet (further details in section 3.1),*
- *Provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data,*
- *Metadata⁸ of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.*

It is important to include in the metadata all the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”,

⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/> OpenAIRE is a Non-Profit Partnership, established in 2018 as a legal entity, OpenAIRE A.M.K.E, to ensure a permanent open academic communication infrastructure to support European research.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/> Zenodo is an open repository developed by the OpenAIRE program and managed by CERN.

⁶ Free online access for any user

⁷ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

⁸ Metadata refers to the information that describes the dataset (i.e. author(s), publication date, size, etc.). Most of the open platforms offer repositories that use standard metadata systems.

- the name of the action, acronym and grant number,
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable and a persistent identifier⁹.

The screenshot shows a web form for Zenodo metadata. The top section is titled 'Related/alternate identifiers' and has a 'recommended' dropdown menu. Below the title, there is a text box with the instruction: 'Specify identifiers of related publications and datasets. Supported identifiers include: DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs and URLs.' There is a label 'Related identifiers' followed by a text input field containing 'e.g. 10.1234/foobar.56789', a dropdown menu, and another dropdown menu containing 'N/A'. Below this is a small text: 'Optional. Resource type of the related identifier.' At the bottom of this section is a '+ Add another related identifier' link. Below the main section are several tabs: 'Contributors', 'References', 'Journal', 'Conference', 'Book/Report/Chapter', 'Thesis', and 'Subjects', each with an 'optional' label and a right-pointing arrow. At the bottom of the form are three buttons: 'Delete', 'Save', and 'Publish'.

Figure 1. Example of Zenodo's metadata (image by Faircookbook¹⁰)

1.2.3 IPR commitments in INTEGER

Apart from the commitments regarding Open Access and Open Data, the other main commitments linked to IPRs included in the GA and the CA are detailed in Article 8 of the CA which states that:

- *Results are the property of the Party generating them. In case of co-ownership, each co-owner shall have the right to exploit the joint results as it sees fit and to grant non-exclusive licenses, without obtaining any consent from any other co-owner, paying compensation or otherwise being accountable to any other co-owner, unless otherwise agreed between the co-owners.*

The regulation of access to background information is defined in Article 9 of the CA.

1.3 GDPR compliance

INTEGER is dealing with personal, in some cases sensitive, data. Therefore, the consortium is setting up all necessary measures to protect its users while participating in the project. For instance, any user involved in any project activity is informed about:

- when data is gathered,
- knowing what kind of data is gathered,

⁹ A persistent identifier is a long-lasting reference to a digital resource. <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360006971013-What-are-persistent-identifiers-PIDs>

¹⁰ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/findability/zenodo-deposition.html>

- how it is used
- what their rights are as a participant in the project.

The project is following the legal obligations of data protection legislation in accordance with European Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016¹¹ and local laws of each relevant partner.

EACH PARTNER, IS SOLE RESPONSIBLE OF THE PROPER APPLICATION OF NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN REGULATIONS AND LAWS IN TERMS OF DATA PROTECTION AND PRIVACY. EACH PARTNER IS RESPONSIBLE FOR ITS ASSOCIATED PARTNERS AND THIRD PARTIES INVOLVED IN THE INTEGER 4H PROJECT TO FOLLOW THESE REGULATIONS.

INTEGER's strategy is to minimise the use of personal data as much as possible, limiting it to the information needed to carry out the action and using as many mechanisms that intend to protect participants (anonymized, aggregated data, etc.). Following this strategy ensures that the risk of harming individual rights is as low as possible and allows for easy use of the data collected for academic research purposes. In relation to the data collected, INTEGER ensures honesty and transparency towards the research subjects and, in particular, obtaining the free and informed consent of third parties. There is no dissemination of personal information without prior written consent of the third parties involved in INTEGER's actions.

All users participating in the project activities are informed of the activity and how the data is used, and are asked to provide written consent confirming that they have read and understood the information provided and have given their informed consent, before the activity begins.

- **INTEGER 4-H Platform:** Any user who joins the project community through the INTEGER 4-H platform read and provide his consent in agreement with the use and management of the data provided in the link https://integer4h.theglobal.network/users/sign_up?co=3e71539329a597cc22816ee12462e47bff9b88f5.

¹¹Council of the European Union, European Parliament. (2016, 27 April). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance). Publications Office of the EU. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3e485e15-11bd-11e6-ba9a-01aa75ed71a>

Figure 2. Privacy statement used in the INTEGER 4-H platform

- **INTEGER activities:** In case the project targets users in face-to-face activities, or users who have not provided their consent through the platform, there is an alternative process. In this case, an informed consent form (available in English) has been developed (see Annex I). This informed consent consists of two parts. The first part explains the activity and purpose of data collection and use, and the second part, in which users agree to the terms explained in the first part, together with how the data is processed and image rights.

No user shall participate in any project activity without having read, understood and provided their consent.

1.4 Data exchange

One of the main features of INTEGER is that three different centres, three *col-laboratories*¹² spread across Europe, work together and each of them collect different sets of data. To achieve this goal, it is essential to have a tool that allows data to be shared between the partners quickly and securely (see section 3.3.2 for further details).

It is mandatory that all data is kept and shared securely, ensuring the protection of users' rights throughout the whole process (and project). Each partner is responsible for implementing appropriate mechanisms for the handling of the data to be shared. All data exchanged or to be exchanged between INTEGER partners containing sensitive data is properly anonymised.

A number of datasets are generated throughout the life of the project, some of which contain personal or sensitive data of external users involved in the project activities. For the purposes

¹² It is a neologism for the next generation of quadruple or n-helix living labs. (<https://integercollab.eu/what-is-integer/>)

of the project, or following the principle of open science, it is necessary to share this data (e.g., as part of research publications) ensuring that no data leaks or security violations occur.

1.5 Data security

To protect the data generated, used or processed during the INTEGER project it is important to understand the potential threats, align the layers of defence and understand the activities related to data management and protection during the life of the project and take the necessary measures.

INTEGER follows the five pillars of information security¹³ to ensure adequate security in the management of its data: confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity and non-repudiation.

1. Confidentiality: To consider data protection is to ensure the confidentiality of data. To do so, it is essential to encrypt the data and restrict access so that only authorized persons can access them.
2. Integrity: To guarantee the integrity of the data, it is essential to prevent third parties from manipulating INTEGER's information system, thus avoiding the alteration, modification or destruction of the information.
3. Availability: For the information system to function, it is important that authorised persons can access and have access to the data. For this it is important that the information services used in INTEGER are robust and functional, avoiding crashes or malfunctions.
4. Authenticity: It is important that users confirm their identity through an authenticity system, such as a double authenticity system, to secure the transmission of information and access to INTEGER's systems and resources.
5. Non-repudiation: When sharing information, it is important that both sender and receiver have confirmation not only of receipt, but also that the identities of each are authorised, and it is the system that makes it impossible to deny sending, receiving, or accessing data, as this is recorded.

Each partner (and possibly linked third parties -any legal entity which has a legal link to a beneficiary implying collaboration that is not limited to the action-) is responsible for ensuring compliance with all these principles during the project. In addition to the above considerations, the development of INTEGER's data protection activities follow and take into account the consortium partners' own data security policies.

The I2CAT Foundation, as Project Coordinator, acts as Data Protection Coordinator (DPC) of the project, assisted by the single point of contact for data privacy of each of the consortium members (Data Protection Officers, DPO), to manage such data. This responsibility does not prevent the partners from having their own data protection roles, always following their own data protection rules, regional regulations and GDPR.

¹³ *The 5 pillars of information security and how to manage them.* (2022, July 18). Infnit-O Resource Center. <https://resourcecenter.infnit-o.com/blog/the-5-pillars-of-information-security-and-how-to-manage-them/>

1.6 Archiving and preservation

While INTEGER is active and following the security guidelines of the previous section (see 1.4), the raw data produced by the project is stored by the partners themselves according to their need or convenience. After the end of the project, the consortium will have chosen a secure repository where the overall INTEGER project data will be stored and preserved.

The project foresees the use of Zenodo as a platform to store and manage the generated data and Open Aire to link the databases and publications. In addition, the project disseminates the open results through its website (<https://integercollab.eu/>), its INTEGER-4H platform (<https://theglobal.network/>), and social media..

As stated in the Grant Agreement (page 11, section 6 Other), the consortium commits to keep records of all documentation 5 years after the end of the project period. In addition, any personal data collected is treated in accordance with the applicable data protection law and will be anonymised at all times.

2 FAIR Data approach

Following the line of the European Commission in its data strategy¹⁴ that pursues cloud-based knowledge fostered by open access data, the INTEGER project is committed to follow the guidelines of the Horizon Europe programme and make all its data as open as possible following the FAIR principles. Therefore, this document describes how all the data is managed and treated, regarding different kinds of documents, datasets, etc. Moreover, the processing of personal data and its correct anonymisation follows the guidelines set out in the Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement, and the local and European legislations.

2.1 Introduction: What is FAIR?

Projects such as INTEGER can generate data that require appropriate management, storage and processing for their use. As the scientific community is already committed to Open Science, a set of best practices for the management and publication of scientific data is required.

Wilkinson et al. (2016)¹⁵ posit that data brought about a change in the way open access data was treated and published, creating a guide to ensure that digital publications are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and ensure Reusability of resources.

2.2 INTEGER measures to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable

Having explained in the previous section what FAIR data are, the following section explains how the INTEGER project follows and implement these processes and how the guidelines established in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement are followed, as well as respecting the local and European legislation on the processing of personal data and ensuring their correct anonymisation.

2.2.1 Findable

In order to make the data to be findable, i.e. the community can easily find the datasets on online platforms through search tools, the consortium commits to assign to only public data a Digital Object Identifier (DOI¹⁶) to the data. In addition, all datasets must be adequately described according to a metadata schema, such as Dublin Core Specifications and Schemas¹⁷.

INTEGER deposits all its publications that can be shared without restriction in a centralised repository accessible on the web. The most prominent option at present is the open data portal managed by OpenAIRE, Zenodo. This portal allows researchers to publish in a variety of formats and typologies, such as articles, presentations or datasets. It also assigns a DOI to each publication, making it easy for researchers to register.

¹⁴ *European data strategy*. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en#projected-figures-2025

¹⁵ Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., ... & Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), 1-9.

¹⁶ <https://www.doi.org/>

¹⁷ *DublinCore*. <https://www.dublincore.org/>

2.2.2 Accessible

In line with the open data policy, INTEGER is committed to ensuring access to all datasets it generates, collects or produces during the life of the project.

Although due to the sensitivity of some of the data that may be generated through data collection in the project activities, these may not be published until they are properly processed or have certain access restrictions to ensure GDPR compliance. While not all data contained in the datasets is fully open access, the metadata describing them are they.

2.2.3 Interoperable

The use of open software and controlled vocabularies, as well as the avoidance of ontologies that are not in common use, are examples of the project's approach to interoperability.

The nature or source of the data comes mainly from the different face-to-face or online activities developed during the project, such as webinars, co-creation sessions, col-laborathons, study visits, workshops, events, mentoring and training sessions, etc. An important source of data is also the INTEGER platform, the participation of members and their interactions.

All data entered by users of the platform is standardised in a recognized format. Additionally, there is structured metadata – consistent metadata to describe user-generated content (including information on who posted it when it was posted, relevant topics, etc.). All of this information comes from the platform's analytics tools.

Vocabulary has been categorized , so it can be referred to the 'What we mean when we say' section on the website, which is also used on the platform and in all materials produced. So, if anyone wants to produce some material using this data, s/he can easily find information by searching for this vocabulary.

The data from the platform and other tools that have been used can be exported as Google Forms or Drive documents, so that it is possible to import/export and exchange information with it.

All this information and data helps the consortium to prepare, for instance, future events, as well as to develop the INTEGER 4H Col-laborative Working Model .

2.2.4 Re-usable

INTEGER is committed to licensing the datasets to third parties under the most appropriate license, taking into account the intellectual property rights of the project partners as defined in the consortium agreement.

In application of European Commission policy, Open Research Europe strongly recommends using a certified or trusted community-recognised repository as the first choice for depositing data. Where no community-recognised repository exists, a trusted general data repository (such as Zenodo), an institutional repository or a national repository should be chosen.

In addition to ensuring proper licensing and data repository selection, the project website <https://integercollab.eu> as well as the digital space platform <https://integer4h.theglocal.network> serve as a central hub for disseminating project updates,

findings, and resources. Both provide stakeholders with easy access to project and activities information and serve as meeting points for fostering collaboration and engagement within the research community.

3 Data Management

The DMP defines how the data to be generated by the project is stored, located and preserved and in which cases it is publicly disclosed. This DMP follows the guidelines of the Digital Curation Centre (www.dcc.ac.uk) on how to implement DMPs and the EC recommendations published in the FAIR Guidelines.

3.1 Purpose of Data Collection and its Relation to the Project Objectives

The data generated in the project has been created through workshops, publications and other types of face-to-face or online activities, synchronous or asynchronous, related to the project objectives, as indicated below:

- **WP1-COORDINATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING:** The datasets generated in WP1 are limited to contact lists (e.g. mailing lists), so it can be considered that no open datasets are generated within this WP.
- **WP2-LEARNING FOR 4-H COLLABORATORY CO-CREATION; WP3-REGIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS 'AS COLLABORATORY TESTBEDS'; WP4-INTEGER 4-H MODEL & EU HEALTHY LIVING COLLABORATORY DEPLOYMENT:** WP2, WP3 and WP4 are the core of the project, where most of the datasets are generated, given the interrelated nature of the work between the three core work packages (WP) of the project. A wide variety of formats can be found here, ranging from lists of participants in project events, minutes, photographs, questionnaires, data collected at events, session recordings, presentations, posters and public documentation (e.g. the INTEGER core model).
- **WP5-ENGAGEMENT, OUTREACH, AND IMPACT MAXIMISATION:** This WP overlaps with the previous block of WPs, as some content is produced through the tasks. In particular, multimedia content is generated and shared as open datasets. Publications, such as papers or research articles, are also open outcomes in most cases.

3.2 Data identification

During the lifetime of the INTEGER project several datasets are being produced by various members of the consortium, representing different domains. For each open dataset, the consortium provides a valid licence or proof of ownership. In its design, INTEGER remains compliant with GDPR¹⁸ and the ePrivacy and NIS directives¹⁹. However, the consortium recognises that the need may arise to openly publish other data generated by the project. In such a case, the consortium prioritises the use of standardised and interoperable data and file formats wherever possible. In cases of unstructured and non-standardised data, the consortium implements a data format that is published as an INTEGER specification.

Datasets shall be described by: *Name of the Dataset, Reference, Ownership, Level of Public Access, Description, Data Types, Data Formats & Size, Archiving, Curation & Preservation*

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32002L0058>

¹⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis2-directive>

Mechanism, Source of the Data, Are the data reused or owned? Whether it contains sensitive data (according to data protection law, such as personal data), and Use for the Project.

The data, however, is not made public if there are security, confidentiality, privacy and/or data protection concerns.

The datasets that generated are listed below in Table 1. It is possible, as the project evolves, this table is modified with additions or removals of datasets.

Field	Description
Name of the Dataset	Dataset name
Reference	<i>WPx_Tx_title_year_month_verx_PARTNER_dataset.ext</i>
Ownership	Institution's contact person for data management
Level of Public Access	The level of access must be one of the following: Open (data are made publicly available to third parties, with or without restrictions); Restricted (data are only available to consortium members, and the EU Commission for review and evaluation purposes if needed).
Description	Brief description of the datasets that have been identified by the consortium partners as relevant for the different trials.
Data Types	Text, videos, personal data, images, names, contacts
Data Formats & Size	Format of the data format (.pdf, .doc, .xls, etc.). Specific tools or software (if needed) and size of the files included in the dataset.
Archiving	Where the data is stored.
Curation & Preservation Mechanism	DOI and preservation mechanisms of the dataset.
Source of the Data	Where, how or when the data originates. It may also be due to a project, industry, person, study, etc.
Re-used/Owned	If a dataset already published in the project is used, cite it correctly specifying access, location and ownership of use.
Sensitive Data	Yes or No. If YES, notify the Data Manager and check what measures are applied.

Table 1. Example of a description of datasets

It is necessary to record possible changes that occur during the execution of INTEGER and that affect the information described in this deliverable. We periodically check and update to ensure that the information is up to date. This update is done online (via email), where the i2CAT Foundation Data Manager reminds partners to check existing datasets or update them with new ones. We document an updated (and consolidated) list of datasets in a spreadsheet stored in the INTEGER repository (hosted by i2CAT Foundation). Only project partners can access it at any time for consultation purposes or to update the available information.

4 Internal Procedures and Resources

4.1 Consortium Roles and Coordination

To monitor and manage the project data, it is important to define and establish a governing body. A structure to coordinate all partners to provide support when needed and to identify possible risks or errors in data processing.

This is the proposed organisational structure for INTEGER (see Figure 3).

Data Protection Coordinator, DPC (i2CAT Foundation): Within the coordinating entity, one person is appointed as DPC, whose main objective is to keep track of possible project datasets and ensure that they are updated in the data control sheet, advises partners on the basis of information provided by the PMO (Project Management Office at i2CAT Foundation), supports the use of storage tools, coordinates the preparation of the data management plan, and provides status reports on request.

Project Management Office, PMO (i2CAT Foundation): In charge of all legal and administrative issues related to INTEGER. It supports the partners (via the DPC) on GDPR and data management issues.

Data Protection Officer, DPO (all partners): To have clearly defined roles, each partner identifies a person in charge of data management and data protection within their organisation. This person interacts with the DPC.

Figure 3. Organisational structure for data management in INTEGER

The DPC is expected to contact all DPOs at least twice a year to update the datasets and ensure that they are accessible to the project audience. Any DPO can approach the DPC for consultation at any time. The contact person is introduced to the project partners and his/her contact details are available on the project platform and in the dataset identification file.

Name	Email	Entity
i2CAT responsible (DPC)	marta.martorell@i2cat.net	i2CAT
i2CAT EPO department (DPO)	rebd@i2cat.net	i2CAT
Rebeca Martín (DPO)	rebeca_martin@fundacio.ury.cat	FURV
Javier Ganzarain (DPO)	javier@afedemy.eu	AFE
Luis Dias (DPO)	luisdias@shine2.eu	SHINE
Stuart Anderson (DPO)	privacyie@f6s.com	F6S
Kai Fritze (DPO)	kai.fritze@soziales.hamburg.de	HAM
Monika Tokarczyk (DPO)	iod@uj.edu.pl	UJ
Aleksandra Słowik-Mastalska (DPO)	iod@kpt.krakow.pl	KTP

Table 2. List of DPOs per entity (July'24)

4.2 Data storage, sharing and protection tools

INTEGER uses two tools to share data, knowledge and documents between project partners: Google Drive²⁰ and the INTEGER platform – Integer 4-H²¹.

- **Google Drive:** It is the main tool for storing, sharing and editing documentation provided by i2CAT Foundation as project coordinator. All project partners have access to the project folders. Google Drive is a well-known solution for file management as well as for online editing. Google Drive was also chosen because it is compatible with the INTEGER platform.
- **INTEGER 4-H:** INTEGER 4-H is the platform customised for the purposes of the project. One of its functionalities is to facilitate the storage and sharing of information and documentation, including publications, presentations, and other datasets. It is used to store the final documentation and to complement other (external) tools.

In addition to these resources provided by the project, there are other tools and resources that are used throughout the project, namely Google Forms, which are used to collect information internally and externally.

Each partner is responsible for putting in place appropriate mechanisms for handling the data to be shared. All data to be shared between INTEGER partners containing sensitive data is properly anonymised. For this purpose, the use of the Amnesia tool²², managed by OpenAIRE, is recommended.

OpenAIRE offers other tools such as Argos²³ for data processing and Zenodo²⁴ for data publishing, tools that are encouraged to be used within INTEGER.

²⁰ <https://www.google.com/drive/>

²¹ <https://integer4h.theglobal.network/company/smart-integer>

²² Terrovitis, M., Tsitsigkos, D., & Dimakopoulos, N. (n.d.). *Amnesia Anonymization tool*. Amnesia Anonymization Tool - Data anonymization made easy. <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/index.html>

²³ OpenAIRE. *Argos*. <https://argos.openaire.eu/user-guide>

²⁴ OpenAIRE - CERN. *Zenodo*. Research. Shared. <https://zenodo.org/>

I2CAT Foundation provides support and advice on data identification and processing operations in its role as DPC. It is available to partners and send emails for reminders and follow-up on the correct identification of possible datasets generated by INTEGER.

4.2.1 Zenodo community

Currently, there is already a community, within ZENODO <https://zenodo.org>, created by the coordinator, where documentation can be uploaded and stored for the scientific community for a long period of time. This community hosts the public deliverables of the INTEGER and all other relevant materials not available in open access repository sites.

Collection URL:
https://zenodo.org/communities/integer4h_101096563/
The above address links directly to the INTEGER community collection.
Upload URL:
https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=integer4h_101096563
The above address will automatically ensure that people using it add their record to the INTEGER community collection.
Curation URL:
https://zenodo.org/communities/integer4h_101096563/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest
The above address links to INTEGER's private curation URL. You will find all pending INTEGER curation uploads.
Collecting URL:
https://zenodo.org/oai2d?verb=ListRecords&set=user-integer4h_101096563&metadataPrefix=oai_dc
The above address links to an OAI-PMH feed, which can be used by other digital repositories to collect this community.

Table 3 INTEGER links to Zenodo (some links are hidden for security reasons)

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard pmo@2c...

INTEGER INTEGER: Interconnecting 4 Helix innovation ecosystems in european regions [New upload](#)

Records Requests Members Settings About

13 results found Sort by Newest

April 28, 2023 (v1.0) Project deliverable Open

INTEGER_D5.1 Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholders' Engagement Plan
SHINE 2Europe RCR

The Deliverable describes the engagement and outreach plan (E&O plan) and includes a clear communication policy, detailed map of the target audiences and key messages, appropriate dissemination channels, communication calendar, resources, and responsibilities of the partners in the INTEGER project. Also, this deliverable defines dissemination a...

Part of INTEGER: Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation ecosystems in european regions

Uploaded on July 28, 2024 2 1

January 30, 2024 (v1) Project deliverable Open

INTEGER_D4.1 First Draft of comprehensive 3H and 4H Integration Innovations Ecosystems Model
iCAT RCR

The document describes the process of defining a comprehensive quadruple helix model within the new generation of living labs that the INTEGER project is piloting and experimenting with active & relevant actors from the quadruple helix spectrum from the three European regions (Catalonia, Krakow and Hamburg) from INTEGER project. The basic princ...

Part of INTEGER: Interconnecting 4 Helix innovation ecosystems in european regions

Uploaded on July 28, 2024 7 1

February 28, 2024 (v10) Project deliverable Open

INTEGER_D3.4 Three (3) Collaborations Final Reports
F&S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED

This deliverable presents the 3 Col-laborathons that successfully made it as the 3 top ranked projects selected in the 3 regional Col-laborathons. The document also details how the regional events went, namely the methodology, objectives, outcomes and lessons learned. These regional events provided a good opportunity to showcase common challenge...

Part of INTEGER: Interconnecting 4 Helix innovation ecosystems in european regions

Uploaded on July 28, 2024 2 1

Figure 4. Zenodo Community hosts publications of the project.

The public documents generated within the INTEGER project have been uploaded as well to the INTEGER website (<https://integercollab.eu/reports/>) and will be updated whenever a new deliverable is officially approved.

5 Datasets

5.1 i2CAT Foundation

- **Platform (Private):** A virtual space where participants can connect with other innovators, share information and resources, collaborate on projects, and foster conversation and opportunity development.
- **INTEGER Key stakeholders' inputs for the Innovation '4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!' event (Private):** This is a survey in the context of the INTEGER project activities with the aim to collect stakeholders' contribution regarding the need for healthy living in their region.
- **INTEGER project: "Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!" event (Private):** This is the form that was used for stakeholders to select their preferred challenge for the 'Let's Hack Together!' event.
- **Feedback form INTEGER Model Event Participants WP4_T4.2_Kfeedback from INTEGER Model Event (Private):** This feedback form is addressed to the participants of 'Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!' during the two moments of virtual interaction together, the 17 and 25 May and intermediate exchange and co-creation through the INTEGER platform.
- **INTEGER_WP4 Reporting (Private):** This Excel is for WP4 Reporting and is related to the EU Flagships.
- **INTEGER Analytics Platform (Private):** This document provides the platform interactivities from different points of views.

- **INTEGER Model review (Private):** A document that defines the INTEGER Collaborative 4H Working Model reviewed in three different meetings; the first between the INTEGER partners (April 17th), the second with key EU stakeholders (May 27th) and the third with key catalan ones (June 6th).
- **WP2 How to upload content to the platform. Mp4 file (Public)** This video explains the different necessary steps in case some member would like to upload content at the platform
- **Registration survey Catalonia Integer membership form -Winter/Spring 2023-. Gform (Private)** We invited the regional catalan potential stakeholders to support the Integer community through this survey to generate a Catalan list of local stakeholders that support the INTEGER community and project
- **INTEGER Contacts. Xls file (Private)** Document that compile the participants within the integer activities and platform
- **WP2 INTEGER Platform members. Xls file (Private)** Document that compile the INTEGER platform members and their activity
- **WP2 registered platform members on Feb 2nd 2024. Pptx file (Private)** Document that helps to visualize the INTEGER platform members and their regional location
- **WP2 INTEGER Analytics TheGlocalNetwork Jan 11th 2024. Xls file (Private)** Document that compile number of platform activities
- **WP2 INTEGER Analytics TheGlocalNetwork Jan 11th 2024. Pptx file (Public)** Document that helps to visualize the platform activity

5.2 URV and FURV

- **Contacts of Business Drivers (Private):** The document compiles the contact details of the business drivers that the URV and the FURV have collected and contacted. In addition, the follow-up and topics of interest of each actor are shown.
- **Datasets related to participation in training materials (audio-visual material) (Consortium only):** Audio-visual material produced by the actors of the business drivers.
- **Hackathon participating projects (Private):** This document compiles information on the projects that participated in the hackathon organised by INTEGER. It includes details about the projects, team members, project objectives, and the progress made during the hackathon. The information is kept confidential and used exclusively for internal project monitoring and evaluation purposes.
- **Catalonia Col-laborathon evaluation questionnaire (private):** This is a form designed to gather opinions, suggestions, and evaluations from participants in the Catalonia Col-laborathon event. The form allows organisers to obtain valuable information about attendees' experiences, identify areas for improvement, and measure overall satisfaction with the event. Feedback can include aspects such as organisation, content, opinions, activities, and more.
- **Incubation/acceleration participating projects in mentorship sessions (private):** This document details the projects participating in the mentorship sessions organised by INTEGER. It collects information on each project's objectives, progress made, and the feedback and recommendations provided by the mentors. All information gathered

- during the mentorship sessions will be kept confidential to protect the participants' privacy and ensure the integrity of the mentorship process.
- **Initial incubation/acceleration questions INTEGER (private):** Personal data of the people and projects that start the incubation.
 - **Registration INTEGER Interregional training: How to sell with AI and LinkedIn (private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.
 - **Registration 2nd INTEGER Interregional training: Communicate, Impact, and transform: The Im-Perfect Pitch (private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.
 - **Questionnaire workshop "Communicate, Impact, and Transform: The Im-Perfect Pitch" (private):** Feedback from the participants in the workshop.
 - **Incubation meetings agenda (private):** Document with the dates of meetings.
 - **Summary of meeting content:** In the mentoring sessions, various documents essential for the development and strategic planning of ventures are generated. These documents include the SWOT, the CAME, the value proposition, and the Balanced Scorecard, each with specific functions detailed below. The SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) is a strategic tool that identifies the internal and external factors affecting the organisation. It helps to understand the current situation of the company. The CAME analysis (Correct, Adapt, Maintain, and Explore) complements the SWOT and is used to define strategic actions based on the SWOT results. It facilitates the development of a concrete action plan. The construction of the value proposition is a key process that seeks to clearly define and communicate the benefits a product or service offers to customers. It allows the company to differentiate itself from the competition and attract customers. The Balanced Scorecard is a management tool that enables organisations to measure and manage their performance using a set of balanced indicators. It ensures the tracking of progress towards strategic objectives. Each of these documents collects and summarises the information produced in the mentoring meetings, providing a solid foundation for decision-making and the strategic development of the company.
 - **Final incubation/acceleration questions INTEGER (private):** Personal data of the people and projects that finish the incubation.

5.3 F6S

- **List of participants contacts from Integer_Building_the Model Event:** contacts of the actors of the 3 Helix indicated by regional partners, share between the working groups (consortium only);
- **List of participants contacts from INTEGER project "Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!" event,** share between the working groups (consortium only).

5.4 HAM

- **List of participants Hamburg study visit 30. -31.03.2023 (Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.
- **List of participants of Athathons I 06.10.2023 + 03.11.2023(Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.
- **List of participants inner ministerial meeting on Athaton results (Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.

- **List of participants of our workshops / stakeholder meetings (Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.

5.5 UJ

- **List of participants of our seminars/workshops (Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.
- **List of participants in study visits (Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.

5.6 KTP

- **List of participants of Ahathon I 29.11.2023- 1.12.2023 (Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.
- **List of participants of Ahathon II 13.06.2024- 14.06.2024 (Private):** List with names, surnames and institutions, emails.

5.7 SHINE

- **Datasets related to the project website and social media (Private):** The project website sets up a web analytics service to collect statistics. Only anonymous data, which cannot be attributed to specific individuals, is collected. In addition, social media platforms use their own analytics services to collect and present information related to user engagement on these platforms.
- **Datasets related to external communication with third parties (Private):** Project partners engage and communicate with third parties throughout the project in one or more of the planned activities.
- **Datasets associated with participation in other events, aiming to gather images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination purposes (Private):** The project organises activities for which there is no registration form, and where it may be useful to collect images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination actions.
- **Datasets associated with participation in other events, aiming to gather images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination purposes (Private):** The project organises activities for which there is registration form, and where it may be useful to collect images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination actions

5.8 AFE

- **Video clips of experts (Private):** Several videos from experts, used within the INTEGER video pills.
- **Visual presentations for the video pills (Private):** Created PPT presentations, to visually use in the Video Pills.
- **Text scripts for the video pills (Private):** Created text scripts in Word files that are used for the video pills.
- **Pictures and licences (Private):** Pictures used for the reports and video pills. All pictures are stored together with the corresponding licences for usage.
- **Audio files (Private) :** Audio files produced by a vocal speaker, used for the creation of the video pills.

- **Registration survey for the Col-laber Training Day (Private):** Results with names, surnames, institutions, 4H sector & emails.
- **Expert presentations of the Col-laber Training Day (Private):** Presentations of several experts that were present at the Col-laber Training Day.
- **Video Pills (Public):** Video pills, published on the INTEGER YouTube channel.

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex I - Informed Consent

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1W_w2Eu6_Ko9P-R6Gcem1CTKi4S8xxP06/view?usp=drive_link

Figure 5. Informed Consent form

- Background and aim

INTEGER - Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions is a project under the European Innovation Ecosystems cluster, funded by the Horizon Europe Programme, running from February 2023 to January 2025.

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living and wellbeing, INTEGER is bringing forward three important innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive, and integrative European Union (EU) innovation ecosystems: the INTEGER 4 Helix Col.laboratory model; an EU Healthy Living Col.laboratory; a new professional profile, the 'col-laber' or 'col-laboratory manager'.

Based on a peer-to-peer approach between business-driven and social-driven innovations, INTEGER seeks to accelerate transformative integration outcomes by creating new win-win games, local mission-driven synergies, ground-breaking coordination of actions, governance, implementation, uptaking and exploitation dynamics.

- Your participation in workshops, other events or interviews/surveys

Your participation in workshops, other events or interviews/surveys is voluntary. You are free to choose which questions you want to answer, and you may leave the workshop or another event at any time without giving any explanation.

- Use of information collected

We will treat all the information about you with strict confidentiality and in accordance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national data protection laws.

Only the organisation that collects your data, has access to your contact data. When the data collection is completed, all personal data will be anonymised in their further use.

The project partners of the INTEGER project will work with the anonymous data afterwards. This will be done according to scientific criteria and with absolutely respect for personal and privacy rights.

Your name and contact information will be deleted before the data is published and no later than January 2025. The rest of the collected data will be securely stored for an indefinite period, as this is a requirement from EC programmes, and for further research purposes.

We will make every effort to ensure that no participant is identifiable in the project report or in any publication based on the workshops; exceptions are only possible if the usage of the name and/or image is desired to be a written declaration.

One specific exception to the above statement is in the case of the platform (integer4h.theglobal.network), where the data collection is described in the network's privacy policy.

- **Your rights**

As long as we can identify your oral and consented visual contributions, you have the right to object to the processing of your personal data, to access, rectify and erase any information about you, and to ask us what information we hold about you. Once details such as your name and address are removed and thus anonymous, then it will no longer be possible to delete the information you provided, as the project partners will not be able to identify its source.

- **Responsible organisations**

The project partners are:

- Fundació Privada I2CAT, Internet I Innovació Digital A Catalunya (Coordinator)
- Universitat Rovira I Virgili | Fundació URV
- F6S Innovation
- Behörde Für Arbeit, Soziales, Familie und Integration Hamburg
- Uniwersytet Jagielloński
- Krakow Technology Park
- SHINE 2europe
- AFEdeMy. Academy on Age-Friendly Environments in Europe B. V.

- **For more information**

<https://integercollab.eu/>

- **For more information on the General Data Protection Regulation**

https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

- **Contacts**

[to be added by each partner]

- **Declaration of Consent**

Please tick all appropriate boxes and return duly signed prior to the workshop, events, interviews, surveys.

	I declare that I am willing to participate in the INTEGER interview.
	I declare that I have been properly informed about the INTEGER project and that I understand the written and verbal explanations.
	I have been given adequate time to reflect on the application to participate; I have had the opportunity to ask the necessary questions and have received satisfactory answers.
	I understand that I will be asked if I object to being photographed and may choose not to appear.
	I authorise that the images in which I appear may be used in INTEGER's communication and dissemination actions, specifically on social media and on INTEGER's website.
	I authorise the audio and video recordings to be used solely for the analysis of the interview/workshop data and further technical development, unless otherwise stated.
	I consent to the audio and video recordings also being used as learning and dissemination materials on INTEGER's social media and website, as well as those of its consortium partners.
	I know that the information I provide in an interview or workshop will be analysed and summarised by my interviewer. I will have the right to review its final version, as well as its use for INTEGER outcomes.
	I have been informed that the data will only be stored for five years after the end of the project, after which it will be deleted, and that I can access or modify/delete it at any time.
	I understand that my name, or any personal and identifiable information, will only be displayed with my express consent.
	I understand I may withdraw my participation at any time, without having to give any reason, and that I will not be penalised for doing so.

	I would like to receive more information about the INTEGER project and receive the project newsletter at the following email address:
--	---

Please, select only one option.

	I allow my name, organisation, image, audio or video recording to be shared on the platform (integer4h.theglocal.network), social media and website, as well as in different reports and publications within the scope of this project.
	I do not allow my name, organisation, image, audio or video recording to be shared on the platform (integer4h.theglocal.network), social media and website

Participant

Name:

Date and signature:

Researcher informing the participant and collecting the consent

Name:

Date and signature:

-

6.2 Annex II - Dataset list

6.2.1 i2CAT Foundation

Name of the dataset	Reference	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/Owned	Sensitive data
Platform	https://integer4h.theglobalnetwork/	i2CAT	Private	It is virtual space where participants can connect with other innovators, share information and resources, collaborate on projects and encourage conversation and the development of opportunities.	Graphs, numbers	It can be downloaded to xls	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Platform	The data provided by the user will be managed by URBEGI INICIATIVAS SOCIALES S.L, which acts with respect to FUNDACIÓ I2CAT as data controller.	Yes
List of attendees until this point of the Study visit in Barcelona Feb 2023	20230215 INTEGRER & Col-lab Salut i Benestar -Study Visit Indicators-.pptx	i2CAT	Private	Number and typology of participants from the project and previous activities	numbers, results	pptx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	attendances	Owned	Yes
Summary of the co-creatin session run during the study visit held in Barcelona on Feb 2023	20230215 INTEGRER & Col-lab Salut i Benestar -Study Visit feedback-.pptx	i2CAT	Just within the project partners.	Document that summarizes the activities run during the co-creation session between local stakeholders and the integer partners	Graphs, numbers, fotos, videos, results	pptx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	attendances	Owned	Yes
INTEGER project: "Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together!" event	WP3_T3.1_Innovation 4Healthy Living_2023_may_v0.1_i2Cat_survey.ext	i2CAT	Private	This is the form we used for stakeholders to select their preferred challenge for the event Let's Hack Together!	Open answers, text	gform. It can be downloaded to xls	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
Feedback form INTEGRER Model Event Participants	WP4_T4.2_Kfeedback from INTEGRER Model Event Participants_2023_jun_v0.1_i2Cat_survey.ext	i2CAT	Private	This feedback form is directed to participants from "Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together!" during the two moments of virtual interaction together, the 17th and 25th of May and the in-between exchange and co-creation through the INTEGRER platform	Open answers, text	gform. It can be downloaded to xls	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
INTEGER_WP4 Reporting	WP4_T4.1_WP4 Reporting_2023_mar_v0.1_i2Cat_dataset.ext	i2CAT	Private	This Excel is for WP4 Reporting and it is related to the EU Flagships	Text	xlsx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Platform	The data provided by the user will be managed by URBEGI INICIATIVAS SOCIALES S.L, which acts with respect to FUNDACIÓ I2CAT as data controller.	Yes
WP2 How to upload content at the platform	WP2 How to upload content at the platform 2023-06-22 08-42-55.mp4	i2CAT	Public	This video explains the different necessary steps in case some member would like to upload content at the platform	Screen recording and voice	mp4	i2CAT's local servers and platform through Youtube	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Created by i2CAT	Owned	No
Registration survey Catalonia Integer membership form (Winter-Spring 2023)	WP4 Catalonia INTEGRER 4H I Membership form	i2CAT	Private	We invited the regional catalan potential stakeholders to support the Integer community through this survey	contacts & free text.	gform. It can be downloaded to xls	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
Registration survey EU Integer Col-laboratory membership form (Summer-Autum 2023)	WP4 EU INTEGRER Col-laboratory for Health and Wellbeing Membership form	i2CAT	Private	We invited the EU community to support the Integer Col-laboratori through this survey	contacts & free text.	gform. It can be downloaded to xls	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
INTEGER Contacts	INTEGER Contacts.xlsx	i2CAT	Private	Document that compile the participants within the integer activities and platform	Contact, free text, participations,	xlsx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Surveys, platform	Owned	Yes
WP2 INTEGRER Platform members	INTEGRER4H_TheGlocal-Network_users-2024-02-05.xlsx	i2CAT	Private	Document that compile the INTEGRER platform members and their activity	Contacts, free text, log-ins, participations	xlsx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Platform	The data provided by the user will be managed by URBEGI INICIATIVAS SOCIALES S.L, which acts with respect to FUNDACIÓ I2CAT as data controller.	Yes
WP2 registered platform members at feb 2nd 2024	WP2 registered platform members at feb 2nd 2024.pptx	i2CAT	Private	Document that helps to visualize the INTEGRER platform members and their regional location	Members, photos, text,	pptx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Platform	The data provided by the user will be managed by URBEGI INICIATIVAS SOCIALES S.L, which acts with respect to FUNDACIÓ I2CAT as data controller.	Yes
WP2 INTEGRER Analytics TheGlocalNetwork Jan 11th 2024	WP2 INTEGRER Analytics TheGlocalNetwork Jan 11th 2024.xlsx	i2CAT	Private	Document that compile number of platform activities	number of log-ins, participations, members, message, chats, projects, searches, relations, challenges, projects,events, actions, visits, ...	xlsx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Platform	The data provided by the user will be managed by URBEGI INICIATIVAS SOCIALES S.L, which acts with respect to FUNDACIÓ I2CAT as data controller.	No
WP2 INTEGRER Analytics TheGlocalNetwork Jan 11th 2024	WP2 INTEGRER Analytics TheGlocalNetwork Jan 11th 2024.pptx	i2CAT	Public	Document that helps to visualize the platform activity	number of log-ins, participations, members, message, chats, projects, searches, relations, challenges, projects,events, actions, visits, ...	pptx	i2CAT's local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Platform	Owned	No

Figure 6 i2CAT Foundation DataSets List

6.2.2 F6S

Name of the dataset	Reference	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/Owned	Sensitive data
Integer_Building_the Model Event.	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11cIkSPLB4208Tl8y17fxmkYJRMUAF95/edit#gid=421390135	F6S	Private	Contacts from the actors of the 4 Helix.	contacts & free text.	xls	F6S local & project drive.	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over).	survey & partners	Owned	Yes
INTEGER project: "Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together!" event (respostes).	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1HgC43OhCy1UQ981PafoFPYY0ZF-a4xMDFXu9e_hlnZI/edit?resourcekey#gid=1434447637	F6S	Private	Contacts from "Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together!" event distributed by groups of work.	contacts & free text.	xls	F6S local & project drive.	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over).	survey & partners	Owned	Yes

Figure 7 F6S DataSets List

6.2.3 URV and FRUV

Name of the dataset	Reference	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/ Owned	Sensitive data
Contacts of business drivers	WP3_T3.1.b_Contacts business drivers_2023_06_FURV_Datacollection	URV & FURV	Private	The document compiles the contact details of the business drivers that the URV and the FURV have collected and have contacted them. In addition, the monitoring and topics of interest for each actor are shown.	Open answers, text	xls	URV local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Dataset circulated among URV and FURV (5 people)	Owned	Yes, that's why it is not open.
Datasets related to participation in the capability materials (audiovisual material).	WP3_T3.1.b_Capability materials_2023_06_FURV_audiovisual material	URV & FURV	Private	This material will be shared on INTEGER's private platform and perhaps also on social networks, with the explicit consent of the participants.	Audiovisual material	mp4	URV local servers	The audiovisual material will be public, but in the same way the files will be stored on our servers (they will be kept in a secure copy for 5 years after the end of the project)	The data originates between June 2023 and June 2024 online by sending audiovisual material	Re-used	No
Registration INTEGER Regional Col-laborathon - Catalonia (Responses)	WP2_T2.3_ INTEGER Regional Col-laborathon - Catalonia_2023_11_FURV_survey	URV & FURV	Private	Form that collects the personal data of those registered in the Col-laborathon	Personal data	xls	Drive INTEGER	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes, it contains lots of personal info (email, recurrence...)
Catalonia Col-laborathon evaluation questionnaire	WP2_T2.3_Catalonia Col-laborathon evaluation questionnaire_2023_11_FURV_survey	URV & FURV	Private	Form that collects the feedback from the participants in the Catalonia Col-laborathon	Personal data	xls	Drive INTEGER	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
Registration INTEGER Interregional training: How to sell with AI and LinkedIn	WP3_T3.3_ Interregional training: How to sell with AI and LinkedIn_2024_05_FURV_Survey	URV & FURV	Private	Form that collects the personal data of those registered in the Workshop	Personal data	xls	Drive INTEGER	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes, it contains lots of personal info (email, recurrence...)
Incubation/acceleration participating Initial incubation/acceleration questions INTEGER	WP3_T3.3_ Incubation/acceleration participating projects_2024_06_FURV_Dataset	URV & FURV	Private	Details of the projects	Personal data	xls	Drive INTEGER	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Information provided by the participants.	Owned	Yes, it contains lots of personal info (email, recurrence...)
Registration 2nd INTEGER Interregional training: Communicate, Impact, and Transform: The Im-Perfect Pitch	WP3_T3.3_2nd Interregional training: Communicate, Impact, and Transform: The Im-Perfect Pitch_2024_07_FURV_Survey	URV & FURV	Private	Form that collects the personal data of those registered in the Workshop	Personal data	xls	Drive INTEGER	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes, it contains lots of personal info (email, recurrence...)
Questionnaire workshop "Communicate, Impact, and Transform: The Im-Perfect Pitch"	WP3_T3.3_ Questionnaire feedback 2nd Interregional training: Communicate, Impact, and Transform: The Im-Perfect Pitch_2024_07_FURV_Survey	URV & FURV	Private	Form that collects the feedback from the participants in workshop	Personal data	xls	Drive INTEGER	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
Incubation meetings agenda	WP3_T3.3_ Incubation meetings agenda_2024_06_FURV_datacollection	URV & FURV	Private	Document with the dates of meetings	Personal data	xls	URV local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
Summary of meeting content	WP3_T3.3_Summary of meeting content_2024_07_FURV_datacollection	URV & FURV	Private	Summary of what is discussed in the meetings	Personal data	xls	URV local servers	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Information provided by the participants.	Owned	Yes
Final incubation/acceleration questions INTEGER	WP3_T3.3_Final incubation/acceleration questions_2024_07_FURV_Survey	URV & FURV	Private	Form that collects the personal data of the people and projects that finish the incubation.	Personal data	xls	Drive INTEGER	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes, it contains lots of personal info (email, recurrence...)

Figure 8 URV and FURV DataSets List

6.2.4 UJ

Name of the dataset	Reference	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/ Owned	Sensitive data
List of participants of study visit, March, 2023	D2.1 INTEGER-Inter-ecos system hands-on visits plan	Jolanta Perek-Białas, UJ	Private	List with names, family names and institutions, emails	text	xls, doc	internal	on secured space in cloud within the organization, stored with project files with access limited to project team's members (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years when project is over)	Internal contacts, from public website	Owned	yes
List of participants of the workshop during the study visit (workshop part), March 2023	D2.1 INTEGER-Inter-ecos system hands-on visits plan	Jolanta Perek-Białas, UJ	Private	List with names, family names and institutions, emails	text	xls, doc	internal	on secured space in cloud within the organization, stored with project files with access limited to project team's members (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years when project is over)	Internal contacts, from public website	Owned	yes

Figure 9 UJ DataSets List

6.2.5 HAM

Name of the dataset	Reference	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/Owned	Sensitive data
List of participants Hamburg study visit 30.-31.03.2023	Teilnehmende Study Visit	Ham	Private	List with names, surnames and institutions, emails	text	xlsx	internal	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
List of participants of Ahathons I 06.10.2023 + 03.11.2023	Anmeldungen Workshop	Ham	Private	List with names, surnames and institutions, emails	text	xls	internal	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
List of participants inner ministerial meeting on Ahaton results	Teilnehmende Workshop Projektergebnisse	Ham	Private	List with names, surnames and institutions, emails	text	xls	internal	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes
List of participants workshop living labs	Teilnehmende Workshop living lab	Ham	Private	List with names, surnames and institutions, emails	text	xls	internal	Stored with project files (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years after the project is over)	Survey	Owned	Yes

Figure 10 HAM DataSets List

6.2.6 KTP

Name of the dataset	Reference	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/Owned	Sensitive data
List of participants of Ahathons I 29.11.2023-1.12.2023	WP3_T3.2_Organisation and implementation of one Collaborathon in each region_KPT 2023	KPT	Private	List with names, surnames and institutions, emails	text, images, videos, files	xls, pdf., doc., jpg., mp4	internal	Stored with project files with access limited to project team (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years when project is over)	survey & partners	Owned (data was collected in the podio platform).	Yes
List of participants of Ahathons II 13.06.2024-14.06.2024	WP3_T3.2	KPT	Private	List with names, surnames and institutions, emails	text, images, videos, files	xls, pdf., doc., jpg., mp4	internal	Stored with project files with access limited to project team (will be kept in a safe copy for 5 years when project is over)	survey & partners	Owned (data was collected in the podio platform).	Yes

Figure 11 KTP DataSets List

6.2.7 SHINE

Name of the dataset	Reference	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/Owned	Sensitive data
Datasets related to project website and social media	https://integercollab.eu/ https://twitter.com/INTEGERcollab https://www.linkedin.com/company/integercollab/	No intellectual property rights or licensing considerations associated with the datasets. The project website is developed and managed by SHINE as leader of the Dissemination work package and I2CAT, the Project Coordinator.	Private	The project website will establish a web analytics service to gather statistics. Only anonymized data, which cannot be traced back to specific individuals, will be collected. Additionally, social media platforms will utilise their own analytics services to gather and present information regarding user engagement on these platforms	website analytics, user engagement metrics, social media posts and interactions, user-generated content	CSV, JSON, XML, or database exports	SHINE server	Data will be maintained for five years after the end of the project. Data will be stored separately, divided into the website and relevant social media platforms. The project will use password-protected spreadsheets, or secure cloud storage	Project Website Analytics Social Media Analytics	Owned	Yes
Datasets related to external communication with third parties	The task leader will be responsible for verifying the consistency of information and documentation in terms of naming and organisation within the repository.	No intellectual property rights or licensing considerations associated with the datasets.	Private	The project partners will engage and communicate with third parties throughout the project on one or more of the planned activities	Stakeholders' contacts, biographies and photos	CSV, JSON, XML, or database exports	SHINE server	The communications and information exchanged will primarily be stored on the platforms used for this purpose, like the glocal network. Specific information and documentation that is relevant to all partners may be exported and saved on the project repository to enable access by consortium members. Information will be stored separately according to the type of activity that the communication is related to. Such information will be exported as soon as it is available. Data will be maintained for five years after the end of the project. The project will use password-protected spreadsheets, or secure cloud storage	Communication Platforms Project Repository Data Management	Owned	Yes
Datasets associated with participation in other events, aiming to gather images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination purposes	The information will be organised based on each event conducted within the project and stored exactly as it is received by the project team.	No intellectual property rights or licensing considerations associated with the datasets.	Private	The project will organise activities for which there will be no registration form, and where it may be useful to collect images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination actions	Images, names, quotes	CSV, JSON, XML, or database exports	SHINE and I2Cat server	Data will be maintained for five years after the end of the project. The project will use password-protected spreadsheets, or secure cloud storage	Activities, images and audio recordings	Owned	Yes
Datasets associated with participation in other events, aiming to gather images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination purposes	The information will be organised based on each event conducted within the project and stored exactly as it is received by the project team.	No intellectual property rights or licensing considerations associated with the datasets.	Private	The project will organise activities for which there will be registration form, and where it may be useful to collect images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination actions	Images, names, quotes, contacts, free text	CSV, JSON, XML, or database exports	SHINE and I2Cat server	Data related to meeting as images, names, quotes will be maintained for five years after the end of the project. The project will use password-protected spreadsheets, or secure cloud storage. Data related to the forms, as contacts and free text will be maintained until the end of the project. The EU-Survey ensures data security through encryption, access controls, and secure storage. All data is protected against unauthorized access and breaches, adhering to stringent privacy and security standards. The project will use password-protected spreadsheets, or secure cloud storage.	Survey answers, Activities, images and audio recordings	Owned	Yes

Figure 12 SHINE DataSets List

6.2.8 AFE

Name of the dataset	Ownership	Level of public access	Description	Data types	Data formats & size	Archiving	Curation & preservation mechanism	Data source	Re-used/Owned	Sensitive data
Video clips of experts	AFEdemy	Private	Several videos from experts, used within the INTEGER video pills. Stored together with the complete names and the institutions of the experts.	Videos, Word file	MP4, DOC	AFEdemy's internal storage	Microsoft Teams	Videos from the experts shared by email	Owned	No
Text scripts for the video pills	AFEdemy	Private	Created text scripts in Word files that are used for the video pills.	Word files	DOC	AFEdemy's internal storage	Microsoft Teams	Created by AFEdemy	Owned	Yes
Visual presentations for the video pills	AFEdemy	Private	Created PPT presentations, to visually use in the Video Pills.	Power point presentations	PPT	AFEdemy's internal storage	Microsoft Teams	Created by AFEdemy	Owned	Yes
Pictures and licences	AFEdemy	Private	Pictures used for the reports and video pills. All pictures are stored together with the corresponding licences for usage.	Pictures, Text files	JPG, PNG, Text	AFEdemy's internal storage	Microsoft Teams	Freepic.com ; AI generated	Re-used + Owned	Yes
Video pill audio files	AFEdemy	Private	Audio files produced by a vocal speaker, used for the creation of the video pills.	Audio files	MP3	AFEdemy's internal storage	Microsoft Teams	Spoken by a vocal speaker	Owned	Yes
Registration survey for the Col-laber Training Day	AFEdemy	Private	Results with names, surnames, institutions, 4H sector & emails.	Open answers, texts	XLS	AFEdemy's internal storage	Microsoft Teams	Survey	Owned	Yes
Expert presentations of the Col-laber Training Day	AFEdemy	Private	Presentations of experts that were present at the Col-laber Training Day. Stored together with the complete names and the institutions of the experts.	Power point presentations, Word file	PPT, DOC	AFEdemy's internal storage	Microsoft Teams	Presentations from the experts shared by email	Owned	Yes
Video Pills	AFEdemy	Public	The INTEGER video pills, published on the INTEGER YouTube channel.	Videos	MP4	AFEdemy's internal storage / INTEGER YouTube	Microsoft Teams	Created by AFEdemy	Owned	No

Figure 13 AFE DataSets List